

Social media communications and festival brand equity: Millennials vs Centennials

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Abstract: The proliferation of live music festivals in Spain has involved for festival managers the need to differentiate their events, creating brand equity through marketing communications, especially in social media. Given the variability in the ages of festival attendees, the present paper aims at analyzing the moderating role of the generational cohort in the influence of social media communications on brand equity creation and its correlates. A personal survey has been conducted for a sample of 622 attendees of the main live music festival in Spain. Respondents have been asked about their perceptions of festival social media communications, the core variables of brand equity, overall brand equity, and the satisfaction and post-festival behavioral intentions. A structural equations model is estimated and multi-group analysis is performed to test the proposed hypotheses. The present work finds evidence about the moderating role of the generational cohort on the relationships between user-created social media communication and some of the antecedents of overall brand equity of live music festivals. Results support the convenience for organizers to consider social media as a key element in their integrated marketing communications, with special attention to contributing to virality of contents related to the event on social media. This study contributes to a better understanding on the perceptions of the attendees at a live music festival of social media communications generated by the organizers and the users, and their contribution to brand equity creation, satisfaction and, ultimately, behavioral intentions.

Keywords: Brand equity; social media communication; satisfaction; centennials; millennials; music festival.

Article Type: Research paper

1. Introduction

The growing importance of live music festivals in Spain has led to their consolidation as a strategic element in the development of tourism in many destinations. This has been due to the fact that these musical and social events have been attracting more and more people based on the formula of many concerts for a single ticket at a lower price (Vallbona, 2015). A "live music festival" is defined by Leenders (2010:300) as *“an event oriented toward music, where several performers/artists perform live for an audience. Festivals are commonly held outdoors, and most of the time they include other activities and attractions besides the performances, such as food and social activities. Festivals are annual, or repeat at some other interval”*. Many people from different demographic and socioeconomic backgrounds attend music festivals, making these events one of the most characteristic manifestations of mass cultural consumption in today's society. Since festival-goers are multi-generational and the members of different generational cohorts have not shared the same socio-cultural experiences, the different social and cultural events attended by such persons have probably had a different impact on the attitudes, preferences or predominant trends of each generation (Strutton *et al.*, 2011). Consequently, the responses of different generations when stimulated by messages or technology used by a festival organizer may differ between generations.

Event organizers need to understand how the communications they produce through Social Media (hereinafter "SM"), as well as communications external to the organization on SM, can influence the way in which the brand equity of an event is perceived by attendees, their satisfaction and their behavioral intentions. In particular, both researchers and brand managers have limited knowledge of different types of user-created SM communication influence perceptions of brands and consumer behavior (Schivinski *et al.*, 2015).

Brand equity is considered a key element in the generation of competitive advantages for an organization, by reducing its exposure to crisis and competition, and thus contributing positively to its financial results. The effects of brand equity are also known and include most notably

satisfaction and behavioral intentions (Ross, 2006), these being strategic requirements for the success of an event (Wong, 2013).

In order to draw the attention of academic researchers and live music festival organizers to available communication tools that allow them to reach different generations of festival-goers more effectively, this study analyzes the moderating role of the generational cohort in relationships between SM communications, the core variables of brand equity, overall brand equity, and the satisfaction and post-festival behavioral intentions of festival-goers.

Thus, this study assumes that the demographic segmentation variable "age" can generate different perceptions among live music festival-goers with respect to communications on SM. The research therefore compared the direct effect of these perceptions on the communications on the event generated and controlled by the organizers on SM and communications on the event generated externally to the organizers on SM in two generational cohorts (Millennials and Centennials) with respect to the determinants of the brand equity of the event, and how these affect the overall brand equity of the event, influencing attendee satisfaction and, ultimately, their behavioral intentions after the event. To our knowledge, this is the first study to compare the direct effects perceived by *Millennials* and *Centennials* in the chain of structural relationships proposed herein for live music festivals.

2. Generational cohorts and communication

2.1. Generations and definition of their time span

A generation has been defined as "*a cohort of people born within a similar span of time (15 years at the upper limit) who share a comparable age and life stage and who were shaped by a particular span of time (events, trends and developments)*" (McCrindle, 2014:1). Similarly, Dhanapal *et al.* (2015:110) define a generation as "*a group of people born in the same era, shaped by the same times and influenced by the same social markers - in other words, a cohort united by age and life stage, conditions and technology, events and experiences*". In this line, Campbell *et al.* (2015:324) define generations from the cultural-psychological perspective as "*groups of*

individuals born during the same time period who experience a similar cultural context and, in turn, create the culture".

The definition of generational borders is a challenge (Campbell *et al.*, 2015) since, as shown in Table 1, there is no consensus regarding the year in which a generational cohort begins and ends. An added complication is the fact that there is no clear measure of culture, since this is measured at country level. Consequently, it would be very risky to make generalizations regarding the existence of a generational cohort beyond the limits within which the research is carried out (Campbell *et al.*, 2015).

-INSERT TABLE 1-

In research focusing on generational cohorts (Table 1), it is worth highlighting the proliferation of studies on Generation Y, also known as *Millennials*, *Gen Y*, *Echo Boomers*, *Why Generation*, *Net Generation*, *Gen Wired*, *We Generation*, *DotNet*, *Ne(x)t Generation*, *Nexters*, *First Globals*, *iPod Generation*, *Y Generation* (Williams and Page, 2011), *Y-ers*, *Millennium Generation*, *Millennial Generation* (Bolton *et al.*, 2013) or *Digital Natives* (Prensky, 2001). The members of this cohort have been identified as an important consumer group, given that they provide indicators of future trends in the purchasing of brands and therefore their perceptions regarding SM are relevant for companies (Jordaan *et al.*, 2011; Duffett and Wakeham, 2016).

Centennials, on the other hand, are also referred to in literature as *Generation Z*, *Facebook Generation*, *digital natives*, *screen addicts*, *screenagers*, *iGeneration*, *Tweens*, *Baby Bloomers*, *Generation 9/11*, *Generation XD* (Williams and Page, 2011), *Gen Z*, *Zeds* or *Post-Millennials*, the latest generation identified. They represent the consumers of the future and attention has been drawn to the need to analyze their purchasing behaviors urgently in both online and offline contexts (Yarimoglu, 2017).

The literature highlights that Millennials and Centennials participate in different leisure activities to those of previous generations (Halliday and Astafyeva, 2014), arguing that in order to engage these age groups in free time activities organizers should focus on targeting their desire for social interaction, involvement and co-creation of experiences that may also take place in or be facilitated in the virtual world (Skinner *et al.*, 2018). However, the characteristics of Millennials

and Centennials differ (Bencsik *et al.*, 2016), since the identity of each generation is acquired through life factors (culture, technology, society, media and events) that impact their attitudes, viewpoints, needs and expectations (Rasmussen, 2015). Millennials were the first wave of the digital generation born into the world of technology. They are highly qualified in digital knowledge; therefore it is easy for them to acquire the use of new technological tools and devices. Their circle of friends is virtual, they mainly nurture their relationships on social sites, they easily accept cultural differences and they like to live life in the fast lane (Krishnan *et al.*, 2012). Money and success are basic motivational tools for them in their work, which are prioritized over family values (Bittner *et al.*, 2013).

In contrast, Centennials, considered the first truly global generation (Dill, 2015), have the characteristics of "net generation" due to the highly developed digital era into which they were born. They are always online on any technical device virtually. They are practical, brave, less competitive but more impatient and more agile than their predecessors, and are continually looking for new challenges and impulses (Tari, 2011).

Today, efficiency in communications targeted at the Millennials segment represents a challenge for companies (Brown, 2016). Strategies, media and communication styles that were effective with their parents are rejected by this generation of "digital natives" (Mangold and Smith, 2011; Smith, 2012), who largely represent the target audience of music festivals. Due to their intense use of digital media, such as computers or mobile devices, electronic marketing has been highlighted as an effective way to communicate with this audience (Adams, 2015). This trend is even more evident among so-called Centennials (Housand, 2016). However, there is ample evidence that Millennials, when determining the merits of a product or service, often pay more attention and give more credibility to the opinions of their friends or other consumers than to the sources of information of companies or traditional media (Smith, 2012). According to Jordaan *et al.* (2011), Generation Y consumers differ from those of other generations in terms of media use, are more resistant to advertising, are fragmented in different media channels and it is difficult to communicate with them. Having grown up in a world more saturated with media than previous generations, Millennials respond to marketing communications produced by companies in a

different way, which implies that marketing managers must reconsider communication strategies aimed at this audience.

2.2. *Communications on SM.*

Major changes have taken place in recent decades in the field of marketing communications. Interaction and communications in society have changed due to new communications technologies, most notably the Internet, with many organizations having become aware of its importance (Berthon *et al.*, 2012), showing their interest and participating in online communities (Winer, 2009), given that this is a key information and entertainment channel, especially for Millennials and Centennials. SM offer organizations and customers new ways of relating with one another (Brodie *et al.*, 2013). Thus, there is a tendency for consumers to become fans of brands on SM, which are a growing source of information on brands, leading to the assumption that SM, in addition to traditional marketing communication tools, have an important impact on the success of a brand (Bruhn *et al.*, 2012). However, to examine the impact of SM communications, it is necessary to distinguish between (a) firm-created and (b) user-created SM communication (Godes and Mayzlin, 2009).

In terms of firm-generated communications on SM, SM (e.g. Facebook, Twitter, YouTube) offer organizations greater capacity to reach their audiences than traditional media (Schivinski and Dabrowski, 2014), due to the viral dissemination of information via the Internet (Keller, 2009). Thus, firms expect their SM communication to engage with loyal consumers and people who can influence their products, disseminate information and learn from and about their audience (Brodie *et al.*, 2013).

Companies are aware of the need to focus on developing personal two-way relationships with consumers to foster interactions (Li and Bernoff, 2011). Hence, SM communication is considered to be an essential element of a company's promotional mix (Mangold and Faulds, 2009). Therefore, in this communication model firms can become more competitive by understanding that their products/services will be targeted at customer networks and not individual clients. In fact, evidence has been found that firm-created SM communication affects brand perception

(Khadim *et al.*, 2015), brand attitude (Schivinski and Dabrowski, 2014) and loyalty (Khadim *et al.*, 2015).

Event organizers must therefore see the Internet as a key component of their future information distribution strategies and take advantage of the wide range of tools (e.g. chats, blogs, YouTube, Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter, Google Wave, Foursquare) available to them to maximize the effectiveness of SM planning (Castronovo and Huang, 2012), always remembering first to understand the characteristics and conversations of the users of such media in order for the media strategy to be successful (Morán and Gossieaux, 2010).

The fact that festivals are held once a year and some are little known prompted Leenders (2010) to highlight the importance of festival organizers keeping in touch with their (potential) audience and other interested parties via Internet, through an attractive website and *mailings*. In this respect, the Mintel report (2013) states that SM are the key information distribution channels for festivals and organizers due to the large amount of information that can be provided prior to the event through such channels, e.g. schedules, artists, etc. (Hudson *et al.*, 2015).

In terms of user-generated content on SM, the tools and strategies for communicating with customers have changed substantially with the appearance of consumer-generated SM (Mangold and Faulds, 2009). As defined by Blackshaw and Nazzaro (2004:2), SM "*describes a variety of new sources of online information that are created, initiated, circulated and used by consumers intent on educating each other about products, brands, services, personalities, and issues*" (Mangold and Faulds, 2009). These media are diverse and include, among others, blogs, forums, social networking websites, virtual communities, social bookmarking sites that allow users to recommend online news, music, videos, etc. Schivinski and Dabrowski (2014:4), based on the OECD definition of user-generated content (UGC) on SM, include under this concept: "*i) content that is made publicly available over the Internet, ii) content that reflects a certain amount of creative effort, and iii) content created outside professional routines and practices*". In this way, consumers produce, design, publish or edit content, making this an interesting and exciting means of communication. At the same time, communication is produced not only for economic reasons,

but participation in UGC activities can be categorized according to users' psychological motivations (rational or emotional) (Krishnamurthy and Dou, 2008).

SM therefore offer opportunities for creating and sharing content among Internet users (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010) that is varied and includes information on brands and products, among other information, and which means that organizations cease to be a primary source of brand communication (Berthon *et al.*, 2009). Consequently, in this information age customers use social networks to access information on products and desired brands (Li and Bernoff, 2011; Christodoulides *et al.*, 2013).

The emergence of SM has allowed individuals to communicate with hundreds or even thousands of people about products and companies that offer them, where in the Web 2.0 era, as highlighted by Winer (2009), powerful communities are created that facilitate interactions between people with common interests, thus increasing the impact of consumer-to-consumer communications in the market (Mangold and Faulds, 2009).

Studies have shown that consumers, especially Millennials, consider SM to be more honest sources of information than traditional marketing communication tools used by organizations (e.g. Karakaya and Barnes, 2010; Kietzmann *et al.*, 2011; Christodoulides *et al.*, 2012). Therefore, to find information, rather than using traditional media, more and more Internet users are turning to SM (Mangold and Faulds, 2009). Such participation in the process of content creation on SM is due to reasons such as self-promotion, intrinsic enjoyment, and desires to change public perceptions (Berthon *et al.*, 2009). Therefore, these consumers who are content creators are likely to be brand advocates and share opinions about brands and products with other consumers (Daugherty *et al.*, 2008).

In terms of the relationship between UGC and brand equity, consumers express greater confidence in product information created by other consumers than in information generated by manufacturers, regardless of whether the information is positive or negative (Cheong and Morrison, 2008). Evidence has also shown that consumer participation in UGC positively influences brand image (Schivinski and Dabrowski, 2014) and brand equity (Christodoulides *et al.*, 2012; Schivinski and Dabrowski, 2014). In this sense, Schivinski *et al.* (2015) argue that users

who are actively involved in the process of creating images related to the brand strengthen their ties with the brand and, consequently, their perceptions of brand equity increase, thus influencing their future purchasing decisions.

3. Research hypothesis

The aim of this research was to analyze the moderator role of the generational cohort on the effect of communications on SM (controlled and not controlled by the event organizer) in the construction of brand equity, defined as "*the differential effect of brand knowledge on consumer response to the marketing of the brand*" (Keller, 1993:8), and the way in which overall brand equity influences the satisfaction and behavioral intentions of live music festival-goers. Thus, firstly it has been argued that marketing communications generally contribute to the creation of brand equity through (a) awareness (e.g. Bravo *et al.*, 2007; Buil *et al.*, 2013), defined as consumers ability to recognize or remember the name of a brand (Aaker, 1996); (b) brand association/image (e.g. Yoo *et al.*, 2000; Bravo *et al.*, 2007; Buil *et al.*, 2013), defined as something linked to the memory of a brand - characteristic, consumer segment, feeling, lifestyle, activity, etc.- (Aaker, 1996); (c) perceived quality (e.g. Bravo *et al.*, 2007; Buil *et al.*, 2013), defined as "*the consumer judgment about a product's overall excellence or superiority*" (Zeithaml, 1988:5); and (d) loyalty (e.g. Yoo *et al.*, 2000), defined as the link that prompts consumers to purchase a brand regularly and resist changing to another brand (Yoo *et al.*, 2000). In the context of event tourism, visitors can use communication media to gather more information about the scheduling of events and related activities while planning their visit (Trinh and Lam, 2016). In particular, in the case of festivals, Manthiou *et al.* (2014) highlight the key role played by firm-created communications on the notoriety of a festival's brand and, consequently, on the brand's value. The viral nature of the Internet for disseminating content is taken into account by event organizers who acknowledge the importance of SM for the creation of brand equity (e.g. Schivinski and Dabrowski, 2014; Khadim *et al.*, 2015), particularly in the context of music festivals (Leenders, 2010; Hudson and Hudson, 2013). Based on the foregoing, the following block of working hypotheses were proposed:

H1: Festival-goers' perception of firm-created SM communication about the event has a positive impact on (H1a) the awareness of the festival's brand, (H1b) the brand image/associations of the festival, (H1c) the perceived quality of the festival and (H1d) loyalty to the festival.

It has been argued that information received by consumers through communication channels not controlled by the organization plays an important role in brand equity creation (Keller, 2009). Thus, consumers consider communications not controlled by organizers to be more credible as they understand there are no vested interests in the communication received from other users (Marks and Kamins, 1988). Interactions on SM allow users to share brand-related information and help them to better appreciate brand equity (Trudeau and Shobeiri, 2016). Various studies have revealed that *on-line* forums related to brands strongly affect consumers' impressions of brands (e.g. Adjei *et al.*, 2010; Marzocchi *et al.*, 2013) and, based on the impact of these social factors, consumers may decide to continue or terminate their relationship with a brand (Nitzan and Libai, 2011). Therefore, given the crucial role of social elements in the determination of the strength and success of brands in the market (Trudeau and Shobeiri, 2016), a second block of hypotheses was proposed:

H2: Festival-goers' perception of user-created SM communication about the event has a positive impact on (H2a) the awareness of the festival brand, (H2b) the brand image/associations of the festival, (H2c) the perceived quality of the festival and (H2d) loyalty to the festival.

Different studies have confirmed the positive impact of the main factors determining brand equity (i.e. awareness, image/associations, perceived quality and loyalty) on overall brand equity. Specifically, some studies have highlighted the relationship between brand equity and awareness (e.g. Kim *et al.*, 2008; Sasmita and Mohd Suki, 2015); brand image/associations (e.g. Biel, 1992; Chan and Liu, 2009; Sasmita and Mohd Suki, 2015), perceived quality (Yoo *et al.*, 2000; Yoo and Donthu, 2001), and loyalty (Atilgan *et al.*, 2005; Bravo *et al.*, 2007), the latter being considered as the main driver of brand equity (e.g. Aaker, 1996). Based on the conclusions of research carried out in different contexts, the following block of working hypotheses was proposed:

H3: The determinants of the brand equity of the festival, i.e. (H3a) the awareness of the festival brand, (H3b) the brand image/associations of the festival, (H3c) the perceived quality of the festival and (H3d) the loyalty towards the festival, have a positive impact on the overall brand equity of the festival.

In terms of the links between overall brand equity and satisfaction, evidence has been found to confirm the link between overall brand equity and satisfaction in the cultural and creative sector (e.g. Huang *et al.*, 2014) and the tourism sector (Kim *et al.*, 2009). Extrapolating the evidence observed in various contexts, the following working hypothesis for music festivals was proposed:

H4: Festival-goers' perception of the overall brand equity of the festival has a positive effect on their satisfaction.

There is broad consensus in literature regarding the existence of a direct relationship between satisfaction and loyalty, which includes dimensions such as the intention to repurchase, word of mouth and tolerance to price increases (Anderson *et al.*, 1994). In literature on event tourism, causal relationships between satisfaction and behavioral intentions are generally positive and significant (e.g. Thrane, 2002; Yuan and Jang, 2008; Kim *et al.*, 2010a, b; Yoon *et al.*, 2010; Anil, 2012; Wong *et al.*, 2014). However, some studies have analyzed satisfaction in terms of both its evaluative and emotional component, showing that the evaluative component is significantly related to attendance at an event but insignificantly with respect to recommending it. As regards the emotional component of satisfaction, this influences the intention to recommend but not to attend the event again. In this sense, McDowall (2011) concludes that satisfaction influences the intention to recommend, but not the intention to return, while Lee *et al.* (2012) argue that satisfaction is not related to behavioral intentions.

The authors of this paper feel it reasonable to consider that the satisfaction of event-goers can positively influence their behavioral intentions; hence, the following working hypothesis was proposed:

H5: Festival-goers' satisfaction has a positive effect on their behavioral intentions.

Finally, Millennials and Centennials are familiar with Internet-based technologies. However, Millennials prefer communication by text or voice, while Centennials, who only know a world with continuous and instant access to the Internet and SM (Williams, 2015), prefer video communication, smartphones and SM (Skinner *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, communications about the event on SM are expected to have a greater influence on younger consumers than Millennials. Hence, the following and final hypothesis was proposed:

H6: The generational cohort plays a moderating role in the Communications on SM-Determinants of brand equity-Overall brand equity-Behavioral intentions chain of relationships, with Centennials presenting stronger relationships than Millennials.

4. Method

To achieve the objective proposed in this study, a quantitative research methodology was developed based on an *ad hoc* survey procedure using a structured questionnaire, in the context of event tourism, and more specifically, a live music festival. The questionnaire included several scales validated in the literature whose items were adapted to the context of the live music festival. Thus, to evaluate festival-goers' perceptions of communications about the event, the methodology proposed by Schivinski and Dabrowski (2014) was adapted to measure their perceptions of communications generated on SM by both the organizers (4 items) and users (4 items). To measure the variables that have traditionally been considered as the basis for the creation of brand equity, and which represent consumer perceptions regarding the brand, i.e. awareness, image/association, perceived quality and loyalty, items from different scales were adapted. For brand awareness, the scales proposed by Aaker (1996) (6 items) and Oh (2000) (4 items) were adapted. For brand image/associations, 8 indicators from Aaker's scale (1996), 4 from the scale described by Netemeyer *et al* (2004) and 7 from the scale proposed by Lassar *et al.* (1995) were adapted; perceived brand quality was measured through 4 items adapted from Aaker (1996), 4 items adapted from Lassar *et al.* (1995) and 9 items from Wong (2010). Brand loyalty was measured based on one Aaker item (1996) and 3 items from the scale proposed by Yoo *et al.* (2000). To evaluate overall brand equity, 4 indicators from the scale proposed by Yoo and Donthu

(2001) were used. Additionally, 5 items from the scale proposed by Rosenbaum and Wong (2010) were adapted to measure attendees' satisfaction with the organizer, location, quality, value and overall result of the event. To measure behavioral intentions, 7 indicators from the scale described by Zeithaml *et al.* (1996) were adapted. All items were measured through 5-point Likert-type scales, where 1=Strongly disagree and 5=Strongly agree. Finally, respondents' classification data were collected.

Data were collected during the celebration of the Arenal Sound Festival (AS), the most important festival in Spain in terms of number of attendees, according to data consulted in the yearbooks of the Music Promoters Association of Spain, with 300,000 attendees in 2017 (APM, 2018). This is an indie, rock, pop and electronic live music festival that has been held on the beach of Arenal de Burriana (Castellón, Spain) annually since the summer of 2010. The questionnaire was given to attendees at the edition of the Arenal Sound Festival by means of convenience sampling outside the festival site, at different points around the event venue and at different times of the day. A total of 631 questionnaires were collected, of which 622 were valid.

In terms of the socio-demographic description of the respondents (Table 2), the sample was representative of the study population, i.e. the profile of music festival-goers, according to data from the Music Promoters Association (APM, 2018).

-INSERT TABLE 2-

For this study, Millennials were defined as persons born up to 1993, as indicated by Schultz *et al.* (2012). Centennials were defined as respondents born from 1994 forward, as proposed by Ortega Cachón and Vilanova (2016) for the Spanish context.

5. Analysis of the measurement model

Based on an Exploratory Factor Analysis, Awareness and Loyalty were identified as one-dimensional constructs, while the items corresponding to the Associations variable were divided into two factors that, in accordance with Aaker (1996), were called "Social image" and "Value". Similarly, the indicators used to measure perceived quality were divided into two factors, which,

according to their content and in line with Aaker's proposal for measures of brand equity (1996), were referred to as "Service quality" and "Perceived quality-Leadership".

The dimensionality analysis was verified by means of a confirmatory factorial analysis (CFA) using a robust maximum likelihood estimation. Taking into account the value of Cronbach's alpha coefficient, three items were eliminated as their exclusion considerably increased this reliability indicator: one item on the Associations scale (ASO15: "Attending AS is well considered by my friends"), one item on the Loyalty scale (L01: "AS is the only festival I go to"), and one measure on the Satisfaction scale (SAT02: "Happy with the location of the AS").

The fit indices obtained showed that the variables converged adequately towards the latent factors (Table 3). The robust index $\chi^2_{\text{Sat-B}}/\text{gl}=1.77$, which was lower than the maximum recommended threshold of 3.0 (Carmines and Mclver, 1981) and the RMSEA value was 0.035, which was lower than 0.08 (Hu and Bentler, 1999). Together with the other general fit indices (CFI, GFI, BB-NFI and BB-NNFI), it may be concluded that overall fit was acceptable (Table 3).

The internal consistency of the dimensions was evaluated considering two indicators: the composite reliability coefficient, with a minimum threshold of 0.7 (Anderson and Gerbing, 1988); and the extracted variance for each scale, whose value had to be greater than 0.5 (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). These indices, which are shown in Table 3, were acceptable for all the latent factors.

-INSERT TABLE 3-

Then, the scale's construct validity for the factors was analyzed. Convergent validity was confirmed for the scales, since all the variables presented significant standardized loading values ($t > 2.58$) and higher than 0.6 (Steenkamp and Van Trijp, 1991), as shown in Table 3. Discriminant validity was checked by verifying that the linear correlation coefficients for each pair of factors were lower than the square root of Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for the corresponding factors (Table 4). This type of validity was analyzed in depth using the χ^2 difference test to test the difference between the estimation of the model that restricts correlations between each pair of constructs to the unit ($\chi^2_{\text{Sat-B}}(\text{gl}=819)=2052.72$; RMSEA=0.049) and the unrestricted model ($\chi^2_{\text{Sat-B}}(\text{gl}=764)=1354.02$; RMSEA=0.035). The value of the statistic $\chi^2(\text{gl}=55)=786.89$ was

significant at 99% ($p < 0.0001$). These results indicated that the discriminant validity of the latent variables was guaranteed (Anderson and Gerbing, 1988).

-INSERT TABLE 4-

In the next stage, any problems of common method bias were checked by applying Harman's single factor method (1976). In accordance with Podsakoff *et al.* (2003), a measurement model was prepared loading all the items in a latent construct. The fit indexes were $\text{Chi}^2_{\text{Sat-B}}$ ($gl=819$)=6266.73; RMSEA=0.103; CFI=0.546; GFI=0.535. Comparing this estimate with the results in Table 3 for the measurement model with the eleven latent variables ($\Delta\text{Chi}^2_{\text{Sat-B}}=6096.30$; $\Delta gl=55$; $p\text{-value} < 0.000001$), it was confirmed that the estimate with a single factor presented a significantly worse fit. In addition, none of the correlations between the constructs in Table 4 were greater than 0.9 (Bagozzi *et al.*, 1991).

Finally, the invariance of the measurement model was evaluated through sub-samples of individuals (Centennials and Millennials). In the first stage, a multi-group confirmatory factor analysis was performed in the two groups, yielding the following overall fit indices: $\text{Chi}^2_{\text{Sat-B}}$ ($gl=1528$)=2272.77; RMSEA=0.040; CFI=0.938; GFI=0.826. Following the recommendations of Steenkamp and Baumgartner (1998), the restricted multi-group measure model that establishes equality in factorial loads for each observable variable in its latent factor was estimated. The fit indices of this estimate were $\text{Chi}^2_{\text{Sat-B}}$ ($gl=1559$)=2311.75; RMSEA=0.040; CFI=0.937; GFI=0.824. Comparing both estimates, the difference between CFI measurements was 0.001, below the maximum permitted threshold of 0.01 (Chen, 2007). Moreover, the increase in the value of the statistic Chi^2 ($gl=31$)=37.65 was insignificant ($p=0.191$). According to Chen (2007) and Cheung and Rensvold (2002), these results indicate the measurement invariance of measurement scales.

6. Structural analysis and contrasting of the model

To test the hypotheses, a model of structural equations was estimated without including the moderating effect of age with EQS 6.2 software. The results of the standardized coefficients are shown in Figure 1. The general fit of the estimation of the structural model was adequate. The

robust statistic $\chi^2_{\text{Sat-B}/\text{gl}}=2.84$ (<0.3), the RMSEA=0.054 and the rest of the absolute and incremental goodness-of-fit indices (CFI=0.870; GFI=803; BBNFI=0.814; BBNNFI=0.861) were close to the recommended values.

As regards the relationships between Communications and the antecedents of Overall brand equity, user-created SM communication showed a significant positive effect on Awareness, Social image, Value, Service quality, Perceived quality-Leadership and Loyalty. However, the Loyalty and Perceived quality-Leadership variables were not significantly influenced by firm-created SM communication.

The main factors determining the brand equity of the live music festival were, according to the positive and significant coefficients obtained in the estimated model, Loyalty, Perceived quality-Leadership, Service quality, and Value. The coefficients for Awareness and Social image did not present statistically significant values.

In terms of the consequences of overall brand equity, Satisfaction depended positively and significantly on Overall brand equity, and in turn, showed a positive and significant effect on attendees' behavioral intentions after the festival, measured as the intention to issue favorable word-of-mouth communications.

To confirm the moderating effect of age, the multi-group analysis was performed for the two generational cohorts studied. The sample of Centennials (≤ 20 years) comprised 244 attendees, while the sample of the Millennial generation (21-41 years) was formed by 374 attendees. In the first stage, the unrestricted causal model ($\chi^2_{\text{Sat-B}}(\text{gl}=1596)=2865.11$; RMSEA=0.051; CFI=0.892; BBNNFI=0.885; IFI=0.893), and the restricted model in which the structural weights of the two sub-samples were equal ($\chi^2_{\text{Sat-B}}(\text{gl}=1616)=2907.52$; RMSEA=0.052; CFI=0.891; BBNNFI=0.883; IFI=0.892) were estimated. When comparing the results, the fit indices of the restricted model were worse than for the unrestricted model. In this sense, $\Delta\chi^2(\text{gl}=20)=42.93$ was significant ($p=0.002$), implying a significant detriment when it was established that all relations were equal in the two groups.

-INSERT FIGURE 1-

Based on these overall results, the significantly different relationships between Centennials and Millennials were identified from the variations in the values of the Chi² statistic if the restriction of equalizing the causal parameter between the groups was eliminated. From the values of the Lagrange multiplier (LM) tests, it was confirmed that the elimination of each restriction caused a significant change in the Chi² statistic, confirming that the causal relationship was significantly different between the groups. Table 5 shows the estimates of the causal relationships for Centennials and for the Millennial generation, together with the results of the LM tests that indicated the existence of significant differences.

-INSERT TABLE 5-

In view of these results, although similar patterns of relationships were observed between the two generational cohorts studied, the multi-group analysis inferred that the influence of user-created SM communication on both quality of service and loyalty was significantly greater for Centennials compared to Millennials ($p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.01$, respectively).

7. Conclusions

The present study focused on analyzing the role of the generational cohort in the effect of live music festival communications on variables that contribute to creating brand equity, and the consequences of the brand equity of the event in terms of the satisfaction and behavioral intentions of the festival-goers. The results of the empirical research carried out allowed us to confirm, firstly, that for both Millennials and Centennials, user-generated SM communications have a stronger impact on the variables that contribute to generating brand equity than communications created by the organizers of the event, in line with findings reported elsewhere (Karakaya and Barnes, 2010; Kietmann *et al.*, 2011; Christodoulides *et al.*, 2012). Secondly, in both generational cohorts it was observed that communications on SM not controlled by the organizers positively affected all the variables that were considered to be determinants of overall brand equity for the live music festival, i.e. awareness, social image, value, service quality, perceived quality-leadership, and loyalty. Thirdly, the results obtained for both generational cohorts also allowed the authors to conclude that the perception of the overall brand equity of the festival by the

attendees had a positive and significant effect on their satisfaction and that this, in turn, positively influenced their behavioral intentions after the festival.

In contrast, Centennials and Millennials differed in terms of the influence of user-created SM communication on the perceptions of the attendees in terms of service quality and loyalty, this relationship being stronger for the generation of younger festival-goers.

The results obtained have certain implications for the management of events in which Millennials and Centennials represent an important part of the audience. Firstly, the return on investment in communications on SM created by the organizers is questioned. Judging from the results obtained in the present study, it is more profitable to hire a *community manager* to enable feedback and trigger the virality of contents relating to the event on SM, since the generations of consumers who are *Millennials* and *Centennials*, like the target audiences of main live music festivals, tend to be more proactive when searching for information and disseminating their experiences through SM, and pay more attention and give greater credibility to the contents created by other users than to those produced by the organizers of the event. SM offer organizers numerous opportunities to listen to attendees, and thus influence their conversations. Therefore, organizers must consider SM as a key element in their integrated marketing communications in order to boost the brand equity of their festivals, in line with Bruhn *et al.* (2012), by increasing the effectiveness and efficiency of such communications.

In terms of the contents of SM communications, festival managers should focus their efforts on creating loyalty among festival-goers and providing tangible evidence of its quality, in terms of both its excellence when compared to other festivals (*best in class*) and the services offered by employees during its celebration, in order to strengthen loyalty towards the festival and the quality perceived by the attendees, respectively, given the positive contribution of both variables to the brand equity of the festival and, ultimately, to the satisfaction and behavioral intentions of the attendees once the event has ended. SM platforms offer a multitude of ways for consumers to interact, express, share and create content about brands and products (Camarero and San José, 2011). Therefore, the combined application of SM created by organizers (inducing Electronic Word of Mouth or "eWOM") and user-generated SM content offer numerous opportunities for

event organizers to create brand equity. Brand managers -in this case the managers of the music festival- could develop, thinking above all in the generation of the youngest Centennials, interactive tools such as online games or applications to not only establish a connection with potential attendees but also give them the opportunity to personalize content and use their creativity in the creation of a live music festival, in which they could make proposals on, for example, festival posters, services, dates, locations, etc.

However, the present study has its limitations, which in some cases could open new avenues for future research. Firstly, the perceptions of the attendees at the event were only analyzed in terms of SM communications generated by the organizers and the users. However, it would be equally worthwhile analyzing these users' perceptions regarding other types of communications, both controlled by the organizers of the event (e.g. advertising, sales promotion) and not controlled by them (e.g. *publicity* -what the media says about the festival-, word-of-mouth communication generated by attendees at previous editions of the festival), and compare any differences in terms of the effect these communication tools have on the variables that contribute to creating value among Centennials and Millennials.

Moreover, data were collected through personal interviews with persons attending the event, while in a study focused on SM communications, data could be collected through an online questionnaire on SM. Additionally, the SM used by each group analyzed and their use in relation to the live music festival should be studied in greater depth.

Future lines of research could be developed to confirm the importance and impact of different dimensions in the construction of brand equity, such as customer experience (So and King, 2010), perceived value (Gil-Saura *et al.*, 2013), trust and commitment (Ellert *et al.*, 2015), thus broadening the proposed axis of this study.

However, as reported by Hudson and Hudson (2013), it is considered that SM will play a very important role in the future of marketing events and festivals, and can also be used to boost brand recognition, sales and profitability, as well as generate loyalty.

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FIGURE 1
Structural equations model

Fit indexes: $\chi^2_{\text{Sat-B}}=2505.94$ (df=882); RMSEA=0.054; CFI=0.870; GFI=0.803; BB-NFI=0.814; BB-NNFI=0.861.
 **: t-Values are significant at p-value<0.01

TABLE 1
Generational cohorts

Author/s	G.I. Generation	The Silent Generation	Baby Boomers	Gen X	Millennials or Gen Y	Centennials or Gen Z	Gen Alpha
Smola and Sutton (2002)			1946-1964	1965-1978	1979-1994		
Bush et al. (2004)					1977-1994		
Lazarevic and Petrovic-Lazarevic (2007)					1977-1994		
Jones et al. (2007)	1900-1921/24	1922/25-1943/46	1944/47-1960/63	1961/64-1978/80	1980/82-2000/03	2000/03-2020/?	
Kumar and Lim (2008)			1946-1964		1980-1994		
Gursoy et al. (2008)			1943-1960	1961-1980	1981-2000		
Steadman (2008)					1981-2000		
Kim, Knight and Crutsinger (2009)					1977-1994		
Lazarevic and Petrovic-Lazarevic (2009)					1977-1994		
Pendergast (2010)	1901-1924	1925-1942	1943-1960	1961-1981	1982-2002	2003-?	
Williams et al. (2010)	-1930	1930-1945	1946-1964	1965-1976	1977-1994	Después 1994	
Strutton et al. (2011)				1965-1981	1982-1994		
Jordaan et al. (2011)					1977-1994		
Mangold and Smith (2011)					1981-1994		
Solka et al. (2011)					1981-1995		
Williams and Page (2011)	-1930	1930-1945	1946-1964	1965-1976	1977-1994	Después 1994	
Gurău (2012)				1961-1980	1981-2000		
Schultz et al. (2012)			1946-1964	1965-1979	1980-1993		
Williams et al. (2012)					1981-2000		
Bolton et al. (2013)					1981-1999		
Valentine and Powers (2013)					1977-1996		
Jain et al. (2014)						1991-2002	
McCrindle (2014)	1901-1924	1925-1945	1946-1964	1965-1979	1980-1994	1995-2009	2010-?
Campbell et al. (2015)			1945-1965	1965-1980			
Cord et al. (2015)					1980-1990		
Dhanapal et al. (2015)			1946-1964	1965-1980	1981-2000	2001-?	
Rasmussen (2015)		-1945	1946-1964	1965-1980	1981-1995	1996-?	
Bencsik et al. (2016)		1925-1946	1946-1960	1960-1980	1980-1995	1995-2010	2010-?
Brown (2016)					1981-1997		
Housand (2016)						1999-?	
Kassaye and Hutto (2016)					1980-2000		
Ortega Cachón and Vilanova (2016)						1994-2009	
Duffett (2017)						1997-?	
McGorry and McGorry (2017)						1997-2015	

Source: Authors' proposal

TABLE 2
Sample characteristics

Gender	n	%	Educational level	N	%
Male	310	49.8	No studies/primary studies	9	1.4
Female	312	50.2	Compulsory secondary education	21	3.4
Age			High school/Vocational training	189	30.4
Younger than 19	93	15.0	3-year Degree	25	4.0
19-22	314	50.5	4-year Degree	271	43.6
23-26	149	24.0	5-year Degree	64	10.3
27-30	42	6.7	Postgraduate studies	41	6.6
Older than 30	16	2.5	NA	2	0.3
NA	8	1.3	Origin		
Occupation			Valencian region (VR)	232	37.3
Student	454	73.0	Spain (other than VR)	372	59.8
Employee	125	20.1	Europe (other than Spain)	8	1.3
Unemployed	32	5.1	Non-European country	5	0.8
Other	11	1.8	NA	5	0.8

TABLE 3

Dimensionality, reliability and validity of measurement scales

Construct (Cronbach α)	Items	SFL (Student t)	CR	AVE
Awareness ($\alpha=0.917$)	The brand name AS is very famous	0.802 (fixed)	0.82	0.60
	The brand name AS is very well known	0.819** (17.48)		
	The brand name AS is very visible	0.707** (14.07)		
Social image ($\alpha=0.786$)	AS fits my personality	0.786 (fixed)	0.79	0.56
	I would be proud to attend AS	0.723** (18.28)		
	In its status and style, AS matches my personality	0.724** (17.17)		
Value ($\alpha=0.836$)	AS provides good value for the money	0.664 (fixed)	0.84	0.57
	AS is well priced	0.765** (19.20)		
	Considering what I would pay for AS, I will get much more than my money's worth	0.835** (17.73)		
	I consider AS to be a bargain because of the benefits I receive	0.745** (16.67)		
Service quality ($\alpha=0.899$)	The employees give me prompt service	0.702 (fixed)	0.90	0.60
	The employees are always willing to help me	0.754** (18.79)		
	The employees are consistently courteous with me	0.799** (19.09)		
	The employees have the knowledge to answer my questions	0.792** (17.80)		
	The employees give me personal attention	0.782** (15.65)		
	The employees understand my specific needs	0.807** (18.89)		
Perceived quality- Leadership ($\alpha=0.832$)	In comparison to alternative festivals, AS has high quality	0.751 (fixed)	0.84	0.57
	In comparison to alternative festivals, AS is the best	0.830** (22.76)		
	In comparison to alternative festivals, AS has consistent quality	0.769** (20.71)		
	In comparison with alternative festivals, AS is the leading festival	0.654** (16.32)		
Loyalty ($\alpha=0.818$)	I consider myself to be loyal to AS	0.735 (fixed)	0.82	0.61
	AS would be my first choice	0.866** (22.69)		
	I will not attend other festivals if AS is available	0.727** (25.25)		
Overall brand equity ($\alpha=0.890$)	It makes sense to attend AS instead of any other festival, even if they are the same	0.767 (fixed)	0.89	0.67
	Even if another festival has the same features as AS, I would prefer AS	0.850** (26.17)		
	If there is another festival as good as AS, I would prefer AS	0.866** (25.25)		
	If another festival is not different from AS in any way, it seems smarter to attend AS	0.795** (22.00)		
Satisfaction ($\alpha=0.840$)	I am happy with the AS organizer	0.725 (fixed)	0.85	0.59
	I am happy with the quality of the AS	0.803** (21.30)		
	I am satisfied with the value of the AS	0.848** (21.56)		
	I am satisfied with the overall AS experience	0.676** (14.91)		
(Postfestival) behavioral intention ($\alpha=0.888$)	Say positive things about AS to other people	0.835 (fixed)	0.89	0.73
	Recommend AS to someone who seeks your advice	0.903** (26.88)		
	Encourage friends and relatives to do business with AS	0.827** (24.90)		
Firm-created social media communication ($\alpha=0.828$)	I am satisfied with the company's social media communic. for AS	0.727 (fixed)	0.83	0.55
	The level of the company's social media communications for AS meets my expectations	0.780** (18.99)		
	The company's social media communications for AS are very attractive	0.761** (16.14)		
	This company's social media communications for AS perform well, when compared with the social media communications of other festivals	0.696** (15.47)		
User-created social media communication ($\alpha=0.845$)	I am satisfied with the content generated on social media sites by other users about AS	0.749 (fixed)	0.84	0.57
	The level of content generated on social media sites by other users about AS meets my expectations	0.778** (20.88)		
	The content generated on social media sites by other users about AS is very attractive	0.740** (18.93)		
	The content generated on social media sites by other users about AS performs well, when compared with other festivals	0.764** (19.16)		

Fit indexes: $\chi^2_{\text{Sat-B}}=1354.02$ (gl=764); RMSEA=0.035; CFI=0.951; GFI=0.883; BB-NFI=0.895; BB-NNFI=0.945.
 **: t values are statistically significant at p-value<0.01
 SFL: Standardized factor loading; AVE: Average variance extracted; CR: Composite reliability

TABLE 4
Descriptive statistics and correlations between constructs

	Mean	SD	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.	9.	10.	11.
1. Awareness	3.99	0.75	<i>0.78</i>										
2. Social image	3.38	0.92	0.40	<i>0.75</i>									
3. Value	3.21	0.90	0.17	0.55	<i>0.75</i>								
4. Service quality	2.91	0.88	0.30	0.47	0.44	<i>0.77</i>							
5. Perceived quality-Leadership	2.55	1.11	0.34	0.72	0.49	0.49	<i>0.75</i>						
6. Loyalty	2.78	1.01	0.26	0.64	0.36	0.38	0.67	<i>0.78</i>					
7. Overall brand equity	3.40	0.84	0.25	0.54	0.42	0.44	0.64	0.74	<i>0.82</i>				
8. Satisfaction	3.65	0.94	0.28	0.57	0.60	0.62	0.59	0.47	0.47	<i>0.77</i>			
9. Behavioral intentions	3.44	0.84	0.33	0.65	0.56	0.48	0.53	0.48	0.45	0.74	<i>0.86</i>		
10. Firm-created SM comm.	3.30	0.78	0.34	0.49	0.46	0.42	0.38	0.27	0.29	0.48	0.43	<i>0.74</i>	
11. User-created SM comm.	3.99	0.75	0.33	0.54	0.41	0.42	0.44	0.41	0.49	0.44	0.50	0.71	<i>0.76</i>

SD: Standard deviation

Diagonal values in bold are square roots of AVE and others (off-diagonal) are correlations between variables

The elements on the main diagonal represent the square root of the AVE

Correlations of paired constructs are on the off-diagonal

TABLE 5
Causal relationships estimation in centennials and millennials (multigroup analysis)

Relation	Standard coefficient (t-value)		ΔChi^2 (df=1) (p-value)
	Centennials	Millennials	
Firm-created SM comm. → Awareness	0.152 (1.93+)	0.214 (3.16**)	0.114 (0.736)
User-created SM comm. → Awareness	0.285 (3.07**)	0.256 (3.75**)	0.503 (0.478)
Firm-created SM comm. → Social image	0.002 (0.03)	0.281 (4.44**)	0.126 (0.723)
User-created SM comm. → Social image	0.773 (7.28**)	0.489 (6.59**)	0.065 (0.799)
Firm-created SM comm. → Value	0.114 (1.35)	0.356 (5.15**)	0.285 (0.594)
User-created SM comm. → Value	0.577 (6.29**)	0.257 (3.94**)	3.381+ (0.066)
Firm-created SM comm. → Service quality	0.048 (0.67)	0.289 (3.86**)	0.401 (0.527)
User-created SM comm. → Service quality	0.678 (7.00**)	0.244 (3.15**)	7.217** (0.007)
Firm-created SM comm. → PQ Leadership	-0.104 (-1.44)	0.167 (2.57**)	0.294 (0.588)
User-created SM comm. → PQ Leadership	0.759 (7.98**)	0.447 (5.90**)	3.244+ (0.072)
Firm-created SM comm. → Loyalty	-0.224 (-3.65**)	0.027 (0.50)	3.372+ (0.066)
User-created SM comm. → Loyalty	0.671 (6.96**)	0.550 (8.34**)	5.639* (0.018)
Awareness → Overall brand equity	-0.016 (-0.30)	0.034 (0.78)	0.122 (0.727)
Social image → Overall brand equity	-0.036 (-0.50)	-0.014 (-0.27)	0.278 (0.598)
Value → Overall brand equity	0.105 (1.53)	0.105 (2.19*)	0.411 (0.522)
Service quality → Overall brand equity	0.143 (2.17*)	0.112 (2.41*)	1.180 (0.277)
PQ Leadership → Overall brand equity	0.337 (4.85**)	0.192 (4.56**)	2.387 (0.122)
Loyalty → Overall brand equity	0.469 (5.91**)	0.650 (10.97**)	0.003 (0.956)
Overall brand equity → Satisfaction	0.567 (7.54**)	0.499 (7.43**)	0.883 (0.347)
Satisfaction → Behavioral intentions	0.806 (10.78**)	0.713 (11.86**)	0.044 (0.833)

**: significant at $p\text{-value} < 0.01$; *: $p\text{-value} < 0.05$; +: $p\text{-value} < 0.1$